

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

Project Number: 823782

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2019

Duration: 40 months

Deliverable 5.20 Training materials of workshop for secure data facility professionals

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	31/10/2021 (M33)
Actual Submission Date	29/10/2021
Work Package	WP5 – Innovations in Data Access
Task	Task 5.4
Type	Report
Approval Status	Waiting the EC approval
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.18

Abstract: This document is the deliverable D5.20 of the SSHOC project and Task 5.4. (Remote Access to Sensitive Data). It is a collection and description of developed canonical training materials and a report from a virtual Social Science and Humanities Workshop held in September 2021.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
0.1	24/09/2021	First draft	Deborah Wiltshire
0.2	29/09/2021	External review, minor edits	Yevhen Voronin
0.3	01/10/2021	Review, minor edits	Elizabeth Lea Bishop
1.0	06/10/2021	Final version ready for submission to the coordinator	Deborah Wiltshire

Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Science	Deborah Wiltshire	Deborah.wiltshire@gesis.org

Executive Summary

Social science and humanities research infrastructures allow the sharing and safe use of confidential data for research. In recent years there has been a shift towards virtual data enclaves or Remote Access or Remote Desktop systems that offer fewer physical controls. They need to be replaced with other safeguards, including often mandatory training. This training aims to ensure that researchers are equipped with the knowledge required to use secure/legally controlled data safely. Developing training is resource intensive so canonical training materials are an economical approach to providing standardised, high-quality materials for researchers. As development moves towards remote access connections that allow access across international borders, having some commonalities in the training that services offer will allow secure data access facilities across the world to be confident that researchers have received high quality training regardless of where they trained.

The SSHOC Task 5.4 Deliverable 5.20 ‘Training materials of workshop for secure data facility professionals’ has two objectives, the first the development of a set of canonical training materials. The aim of the training materials is that any secure data access facility professionals who are looking to develop training in safe data use for their researchers can use the canonical materials as a framework on which to build their own training course. The second objective was to hold a virtual workshop during which the training materials would be demonstrated to a credible audience of secure data access professionals, trainers, and researchers. The purpose of the workshop was to gather feedback on the materials to inform their future development.

A set of canonical set of materials, consisting of a PowerPoint presentation of 94 slides accompanied by a supplementary guide for trainers, has been developed, which builds on the wealth of expertise among UK secure data access services and experience over many years of training researchers in the UK. These training materials were then demonstrated at a virtual, two-hour Stakeholder Workshop on 21 September. The workshop was organized as a presentation of the training materials followed by a small group discussion feedback session. The feedback session consisted of thorough discussions of the training materials with 4-5 participants from the secure data access and research sectors in each group. The nominated leaders in each discussion in the breakout rooms noted the key feedback in Google Documents.

The discussion groups formed a consensus that the materials were both comprehensive and clearly structured and would be a valuable resource to secure data access facility professionals.

Key topics discussion in the breakout rooms included the recommendation that a Supplementary Guide for Trainers be added to the materials to aid course delivery, a discussion around whether there were sufficient materials included for the humanities and around the potential duration and delivery mode of a course. Further discussions also centred around the different considerations when discussing legislation.

The presentations and the following discussions showed that a canonical set of training materials was an important development in assisting data facilities in the safe sharing of secure data. The comprehensive breadth of information included means that discussions demonstrated that secure data access facilities professionals would be able to adapt these materials to suit the needs of their services with relative ease. However, it was also concluded that additional guidance would be beneficial to aid secure data access facilities professionals in the adaptation and delivery of the materials.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation, EU 2016/679
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Science
WP	Work Package
SSHOC	Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	7
1.1 <i>Using Secure Access Data Safely: Developing canonical training materials</i>	7
1.2 <i>The starting point</i>	7
2. Overview of the Workshop	8
3. The canonical training materials	9
3.1 <i>The structure of the training materials</i>	9
3.2 <i>Key points for training delivery</i>	10
4. Key discussion points and recommendations	12
4.1 <i>Questions prepared for each group</i>	12
4.2 <i>Summary from group discussions</i>	13
5. Conclusion	15
6. Other sources and links	16
7. References	16
<i>List of Figures</i>	16
<i>List of supporting documents</i>	16
<i>Appendix 1 - Aggregated list of participants who were registered for the event</i>	17

1. Introduction

1.1 Using Secure Access Data Safely: Developing canonical training materials

Social science and humanities research infrastructures provide a variety of resources and services that researchers can use and benefit from. In particular they provide infrastructure that allow the sharing and safe use of confidential, sensitive data for research. A key part of the security model is to employ mandatory training for researchers in data protection and how to use data safely.

At a virtual event, organised in September, SSHOC Task 5.4 leader GESIS, with assistance from SSHOC Work Package 6 (Fostering Communities, Empowering Users, & Building Expertise), offered a workshop that demonstrated a new set of canonical training slides aimed at helping secure data access facilities to develop training courses in the safe use of secure access data.

1.2 The starting point

Providing access to very detailed secure microdata is not new, there are many secure data access facilities around the world, some of whom are well established. For many, data access is via a physical data enclave or Safe Room, where there are physical controls in place to ensure safe data use. With the recent shift towards virtual data enclaves or Remote Access or Remote Desktop systems that offer fewer physical controls other safeguards are required, such as mandatory training. Such training ensures researchers are equipped with the knowledge required to use secure data safely.

Developing training is resource intensive so canonical training materials are an economical approach to providing standardised, high-quality materials for researchers. As development moves towards remote access connections that allow access across international borders, having some commonalities in the training that services offer will allow secure data access facilities across the world to be confident that researchers have received high quality training regardless of where they trained. A set of canonical set of materials, consisting of a PowerPoint presentation of 94 slides have been developed which build on the wealth of expertise among UK secure data access services and the experience over many years of training researchers in the UK.

The aim of the training materials is that any secure data access facility who are looking to develop training in safe data use for their researchers can use the canonical materials as a starting point. The materials can then be adapted to the specific needs of that facility. Thus, the materials are designed not to be a finished product but to provide a framework on which to build their own training course. The materials are designed initially as a taught course that could work equally for in-person delivery or online delivery. In the supplementary guidance for trainers there are also some notes to aid delivery - these are not intended to be a verbatim script but should guide trainers to the content and its purpose.

2. Overview of the Workshop

A workshop about Developing Canonical Training Materials was held on 21 September 2021. Invitations were sent out to stakeholders within the SSHOC community, and the workshop was also advertised online ¹. Due to the ongoing Pandemic the workshop was held virtually using Zoom, lasting about two hours.

The workshop started with a general welcome, followed by an introduction to the canonical training materials. It was interactive, and the targeted audience consisted of secure data access facility professionals, trainers, and researchers. In total 22 people from the data access and research sectors attended this digital event.

The first part of the workshop consisted of a presentation by Deborah Wiltshire (GESIS), who discussed the motivation behind the development of the training materials and their proposed benefit to the secure data access community before demonstrating the delivery of the materials. The training materials consist of a PowerPoint presentation, which includes six modules covering a range of content considered important to safe researcher training courses. Going through each of the modules, Deborah talked through both the purpose of the module and the content, pointing out along the way where the content or the delivery could be adapted to suit individual data access facilities. The participants had the possibility to address questions in a virtual chat throughout the presentation.

The last part of the workshop contained group discussions. The participants were divided into groups of 4-5 to discuss questions prepared by the organizer, regarding their thoughts about, and recommendations for the training materials. The organiser had prepared four questions to gain feedback, as well as to ensure a focused discussion. The participants were asked to discuss the materials, focusing on whether they thought the materials were clear and comprehensive, what they thought worked well and what topics, if any, they thought were missing.

The participants were a mix of highly experienced secure data access facility professionals, experienced trainers, and researchers with an interest in data security. All participants were very open to learning about the materials and this made for very lively, engaged conversations. Each group noted some key points from their discussion which are discussed in this report and will steer the future development of the training materials. At the end of the group discussions, the participants came back from the breakout rooms, and the larger group discussed some of the key points raised in their group discussions.

3. The canonical training materials

¹ See SSHOC workshop: Developing canonical training materials for secure data access facility professionals; <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-workshop-providing-canonical-training-materials-secure-data-facility-professionals>

The aim of the training materials is that any secure data access facility who are looking to develop training in safe data use for their researchers can use the canonical materials. The materials can be adapted to the specific needs of that facility. Thus, they are designed not to be a finished product but rather to provide a framework on which to develop their own safe researcher training course.

3.1 The structure of the training materials

The training materials are arranged in six modules, each covering a distinct topic as follows:

Module 1 - Introduction

Module 2 - Understanding what impacts data access

Module 3 - The role of legislation in data access

Module 4 - The 5 Safes framework

Module 5 – Statistical Disclosure Control

Module 6 – Service specific protocols

The content was arranged into this modular format to provide a clear structure and easy adaptability. Where appropriate, delivery notes have been included in the PowerPoint presentations to aid trainers in delivering the key messages.

The module structure is designed so that each module builds on the previous module and provides the key concepts required to understand subsequent modules. For example, module 2 discusses some of the factors which impact on data access which introduces the role of legislation which is discussed in module 3. Having discussed these factors, the materials move on to introducing the widely used '5 Safes Framework' as a way of thinking about and managing data access.

3.2 Key points for training delivery

The materials are designed initially as a taught course that could work equally for in-person delivery or online delivery, but the materials could also be converted to develop an online self-study course, and this was discussed throughout the presentation of the materials. The slides include comments to aid secure data access facility professionals in adapting the materials for their own use. These included recommendations for content that could be moved from the presentation into a supplementary handout for participants, to reduce the overall length of the course as seen in figure 1. In some cases, two different slides have been included and guidance given on which to choose for specific audiences.

Legal gateways, useful definitions

Optional: can be included in a course handbook (see notes)

General Data Protection Regulations

(2016) The GDPR is wide-reaching; main concerns include the rights of data subjects, the duties of data controllers or processors, and the liability or penalties for breach of rights

Common Law: The law derived from decisions of courts and case law, rather than Acts of Parliament or other legislation.

Duty of Confidentiality: A duty of confidentiality arises when one person discloses information to another in circumstances where it is reasonable to expect that the information will be held in confidence.

Confidentiality: Ensuring that information is not made available or disclosed to unauthorised individuals, or organisations.

Implied consent: An unwritten 'agreement' between the patient and health and social care professionals that provide their care that allows their data to be shared as long as it is relevant for their care.

Explicit consent: A freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the individual's wishes e.g. regarding data use.

[Welpton, R., Kotrotsios, Y, Parker, S. Data Awareness Training \(securedatagroup.org\)](#)

This project is funded from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020) under Grant Agreement No. 823782

Figure 1: Excerpt from the presentation of the materials at the workshop

In addition, included in many of the slides are some notes to aid delivery. These are not intended to be a verbatim script but should guide trainers to the content and its purpose.

Another key feature of the training materials discussed were the use of group exercises and key places where such exercises could be included were discussed. Group exercises can play a key role in ensuring the participants are engaging with the materials and in helping embed the knowledge using practical exercises. In her presentation, Deborah demonstrated how interactive whiteboards such as JamBoard can be used during virtual courses to allow participants to collect their ideas and responses in a communal location (figure 2).

Breach Exercise - JamBoard

Figure 2. Excerpt from the presentation at the workshop on interactive group exercises

Module 5 covers statistical disclosure control and is the largest module. For that reason, the module is divided into subsections to retain a clear, bitesize structure. Each subsection covers a particular type of statistic, such as descriptive statistics or regression. Each slide covers an example of a type of output and includes an example output, some of the statistical disclosure control considerations and where appropriate guidance on how researchers might address any issues (figure 3).

Box plots

- Shows how data are distributed
- Maxima, minima, and outliers may be an SDC risk
- This may also be true for the median.
- E.g, there are outliers who spent between 10 and 13 years in full time tertiary education
- Outliers stand out and may indicate unusual characteristics that aid identification

 This project is funded from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020) under Grant Agreement No. 823782

Figure 3. Excerpt from the presentation at the workshop on statistical disclosure control

4. Key discussion points and recommendations

4.1 Questions prepared for each group

Each group was asked to consider the following questions when reviewing the training materials:

1. What do you think worked well?
2. Do you think that the course structure is clear?
3. What do you think about the content? Is it clear? Is it comprehensive?
4. Are there any topics that you feel are missing from the materials? What else would you need if you were delivering these materials?
5. Any other comments?

4.2 Summary from group discussions

The participants brought different experiences and perspectives to the discussions which made for engaged and lively discussions. A number of key points and recommendations arose during the discussions and are discussed here.

4.2.1 The focus of the materials

The training materials focus on quantitative data sources and analysis which is primarily the domain of quantitative research more often associated with the social sciences. Some discussion focused on whether these materials would meet the needs of researchers in the humanities. In practice both disciplinary fields adopt both methodologies, so perhaps it makes more sense to think of potential audiences as being either quantitative or qualitative researchers and consider whether these materials will meet the needs of both.

It is clear that these materials will easily address the needs of quantitative researchers, courses like these have been run for a number of years to good effect and are developed to address the issues surrounding the sharing of numeric data sources, deemed to be confidential or sensitive. So, any researcher carrying out such analyses, regardless of whether they are in the social sciences or humanities will directly benefit from these materials. But it is recommended that it is made clearer that these materials are focused on quantitative research.

For qualitative researchers, analysis software packages such as NVivo produce quantitative data. In which case these materials would retain some value. For those employing other qualitative analysis methodology which does not produce quantitative data, the sections on disclosure risk need further careful thought to meet the needs of a qualitative research audience. Current research is ongoing on how disclosure control can be applied to qualitative output, and a second key recommendation from this workshop is that the materials are further developed to include disclosure control examples for qualitative research outputs.

4.2.2 The inclusion of legislation information

Module 4: the role of legislation in data access divided opinions and prompted lively discussion among some of the participants who are highly experienced in the developing and delivering this kind of training. There are two schools of thought, one that supports the inclusion of information about legislation as a means of highlighting the importance of data protection and the role that secure data access facility procedures have in ensuring that researchers do not breach their legal responsibilities. The other perspective is that providing information about legislation is unnecessary as researchers should be encouraged to feel a sense of community and responsibility towards working with the secure data facility staff. The decision on how much information on legislation to include will, at least in part, on the target audience and will be down to the individual to decide how much to include and whether to include content in a presentation or in a supplementary handout. As a continuation of the discussion, one of the participants will be publishing a blog shortly discussing the inclusion of legal information in safe researcher training.

4.2.3 The length of training based on these materials

There was a lot of interest in how long a course based on these materials might last. Among the participants were several experienced trainers and they along with the workshop leader were able to give guidance on course length based on their experiences. It is estimated that for a face-to-face session, a course would typically last around 5 hours and for a virtual course around 2.5-3.5 hours. All agreed that length is determined in a large part by the level of prior experience of the participants, how communicative they are and by the delivery style of the trainers. The key recommendation from the discussion was that guidance on the length of courses be included in the training materials.

4.2.4 Delivery modality of the training materials

Some discussion focused on the different delivery modalities, and which would be the preferred method of delivery. Again, drawing on the experience of experienced trainers present, the benefits of face to face versus virtual delivery were outlined. The general consensus was that the impact of the pandemic would mean that training courses would remain mostly online as it allows people to attend without the burden and cost of travel to physical venues. The training materials have been designed with in person or virtual taught courses in mind, but the clear modular structure was chosen in part to facilitate the transition on developing the materials into an online self-study course. It was advised by the workshop leader, that the slides would require editing to include more detail or that additional supplementary information would be required.

4.2.5 Delivery notes for trainers

Although delivery notes are included in the PowerPoint slides to aid trainers in the delivery of the materials, a key recommendation from the discussions is that a separate supplementary guide for trainers be included in the training materials which includes not just these delivery notes, but guidance on some of the issues discussed in this section. Therefore, a supplementary guide for trainers has been created which includes guidance on areas such as course length and the importance of knowing your audience for developing training courses.

5. Conclusion

The workshop included valuable presentation and discussions and will facilitate further work in the importance of training in ensuring the safe use of secure data. It was widely agreed that the provision of canonical training materials that secure data facility professionals can utilise to develop their own safe researcher training courses would be of great benefit to the international research community.

The materials were well received, and the feedback was overwhelmingly positive. A number of key recommendations were made:

1. It should be clearer that the materials are tailored towards quantitative data access and outputs,
2. Materials should include disclosure control examples from qualitative data,
3. The inclusion of legal information should be carefully considered to ensure it is appropriate for the targeted audience,
4. Guidance on the length of courses could be included with the materials,
5. The materials could be adapted to suit online self-study courses but would require additional work,
6. A supplementary guide could be provided for trainers to aid development of courses and the delivery of the materials.

Following the workshop and based on the key recommendations, a supplementary guide for trainers has been created which addresses key recommendations 1, 3-6. Recommendation 2 remains outstanding as working groups are currently working to develop and guide statistical disclosure policy for qualitative outputs. It is anticipated that the materials can be updated once these policies are developed.

In addition to the recommendations made, there was a consensus that the opportunity to come together to discuss key aspects of secure data access and use and to benefit from each other's experience was a very valuable experience for all. This engagement will form the basis for the deliverable D5.12 Secure Data Facility Professionals Network which will develop a professional network that will be formed from the core group of participants from this workshop and expanded via the networks of Task Partners.

6. Other sources and links

1. SSHOC workshop: Developing canonical training materials for secure data access facility professionals (presentation); <https://zenodo.org/record/5541587#.YVW4kLgzb-g>
2. Workshop Blog; Workshop notes: Developing canonical training materials for secure data access facility professionals; [SSHOC Workshop Notes: Providing canonical training materials for secure data facility professionals | SSHOPENCLOUD](#)
3. SSHOC workshop: Developing canonical training materials for secure data access facility professionals; <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-workshop-providing-canonical-training-materials-secure-d-ata-facility-professionals>

7. References

1. SSHOC workshop: Developing canonical training materials for secure data access facility professionals; <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-workshop-providing-canonical-training-materials-secure-d-ata-facility-professionals>

Further References to the training materials are listed in the SSHOC Canonical training materials for secure data access training PowerPoint Presentation.

List of Figures

Figure 1: Excerpt from the presentation of the materials at the workshop

Figure 2: Excerpt from the presentation at the workshop on interactive group exercises

Figure 3: Excerpt from the presentation at the workshop on statistical disclosure control

List of supporting documents

1. SSHOC Canonical training materials for secure data access training – PowerPoint Presentation
2. SSHOC Supplementary Guide for Trainers for the Canonical Training Materials
3. SSHOC_D5.20_Training Materials Workshop – PowerPoint Presentation

Appendix 1 - Aggregated list of participants who were registered for the event

No.	Country/Region	Job sector
1	Slovenia	Libraries & Archives
2	Germany	Libraries & Archives
3	Switzerland	Research & infrastructure
4	UK	Research & Secure Data Access
5	Netherlands	Research: Methods & Statistics
6	Portugal	Libraries & Archives
7	Canada	Researcher
8	Germany	Libraries & Archives
9	UK	Researcher
10	Slovenia	Libraries & Archives
11	Netherlands	Researcher
12	UK	Research & infrastructure
13	Netherlands	Libraries & Archives
14	Croatia	Libraries & Archives
15	Germany	Libraries & Archives
16	Slovenia	Libraries & Archives
17	Germany	Researcher
18	Netherlands	Researcher
19	Denmark	Research & infrastructure
20	Romania	Libraries & Archives
21	Norway	Research & infrastructure
22	UK	Researcher

23	UK	Research & Secure Data Access
24	Germany	Research & infrastructure
25	US	Researcher
26	Croatia	Researcher
27	Netherlands	Research & infrastructure
28	Germany	Libraries & Archives
29	US	Researcher
30	Norway	Research & infrastructure
31	Norway	Research & infrastructure
32	France	Researcher
33	Germany	Libraries & Archives
34	Croatia	Libraries & Archives
35	Spain	Researcher
36	Germany	Researcher
37	Germany	Researcher
38	Germany	Researcher